
COST VOLUME PROFIT ANALYSIS AND ACTIVITY BASED COSTING TECHNIQUES ON PERFORMANCE OF NIGERIAN CHAMPION BREWERY PLC

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Abstract: The main objective of this study is to find out whether there is significant difference in profitability, liquidity and sales volume in application of Cost Volume Profit Analysis and Activity Based Costing Technique on the Performance of Brewery Industry in Nigeria: A Study of Champion Brewery Plc. To achieve this objective, the above costing techniques were compared using the overhead cost and the cost of commanding units and all sections of the department were appropriated using a suitable cost criterion among brewing products which includes larger beer and malt. The study adopted decision theory as propounded by Blaise and Pierre in 1654. The study also adopted the descriptive research design and data was collected through financial statement of the sampled brewery and the production and audit department of the Champion Brewery. Mann-Whitney U-test was employed to test the formulated hypothesis through the aid of SPSS software at 5% level of significance. The findings of the study show that activity-based costing technique provides clearer picture of cost centers, cost drivers which enables the organization to get closer to true cost and report true profit. The study then recommended that Brewery Industry in Nigeria should develop a good tone of management and core values that will promote the utilization of ABC technique in their costing system. By this, Brewery Industry will be able to determine in a high degree of accuracy the cost per unit of production which will in turn contribute to the overall performance of the firms.

Keywords: Profitability, liquidity, and Cost Volume Profit Analysis and Activity Based Costing Technique

Introduction

In Nigeria, business competition has made manufacturing organizations to become more conscious of their activities and highly technological in a bid to increase their productivity at reduced costs. However, it is extremely difficult to in the competitive business environment without an accurate cost calculation mechanism-traditional techniques or advanced techniques. Organizations aim to achieving business continuity, sustainability and to maximize profitability by adopting a strategy to increase competitive edge in the market place that the organization is operating in. Organizations need to focus on the actions they need to take in order

to remain competitive and survive the current economic downturn (Maiga and Jacobs 2006, in Aduliah and Tareq 2013).

However, Champion Brewery Plc is one of the Nigerian brewery companies that have survive economic downturn years back. It was established in the year 1974 under the name Eastern Breweries Ltd, it began manufacturing in 1976 with a capacity of 150,000 hecto litres of Champion Larger beer and 10,000 hecto litres of Champion Malt. The company was originally owned by Cross River State Government but after the creation of Akwa Ibom, it was handed over to the Akwa Ibom State Government because of the location. The Head office of the company is located at Industrial Layout, Aka Offot, P.M.B 1106. Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

The nature of Business is brewing and bottling of Larger and Champion Malt drink. It was listed on the Nigeria stock exchange on 1st September, 1983. In 2014, Heineken international acquired a majority equity in the company. The company operations now with a capacity of 500,000 hecto litres and the costing method in use in the brewing industry is Traditional Costing system CVP analysis inclusive.

Activity Based Costing (ABC) developed by Cooper and Kaplan in 1980 is a costing model that identifies activities in an organization and assigns the costs of each activity resource to all products and services according to the actual consumption by each: it assigns more indirect costs (overhead) into direct costs. In this way an organization can precisely estimate the cost of its individual products and services for the purpose of identifying and eliminating those which are unprofitable and lowering the prices of those which are overpriced. Cost Volume Profit (CVP) analysis and Activity Based Costing (ABC) techniques use different bases for determining cost for decision making. While CVP analysis decomposes cost into its fixed and variable components based on volume of production and sales, the ABC on the other hand approaches its cost determination on cost drivers identified for detailed level indirect cost activities such as machine set up, material handling, inspection and engineering. Volume based approach for CVP combines the cost of these activities and treat them as fixed costs since they do not vary with output volume.

Invariably, cost determined using these two methods of cost determination will yield different levels of profit, sales and liquidity of the manufacturing organization. The costing method used sometimes leads to either over or understatement of the organizations reported profit, which oftentimes affect the overall performance of the organization. In order to avert such situation from occurring, manufacturing organization should employ a costing technique that would bridge the above gap in the determination of product cost.

Unfortunately, there have been different opinion and arguments by different early writers. There is school of thought (Adeniyi, 2014); Rafiu and Tajiedeen (2012) who maintained that profits determined using CVP are always higher compared to when ABC techniques are applied. To this extent, these school of thoughts have it that not every cost has either the attribute of variable or fixed, instead, there are some costs that fall in between known as semi-variable costs. The same augments go for both liquidity and sales volumes in appraisal of organizational performance.

Conversely, Mazander (2007); Mohamood Amooee and Yaghoub (2012); Nitim and Daigobind (2013) etc insist that profits arrive at using ABC are often higher compared to the profit achieved upon application of traditional management accounting techniques (CVP inclusive). They argue that only costs caused by the cost drivers in relation to cost centres are considered in the costing process.

Meanwhile, none of the two schools of thoughts to the knowledge of the researcher have empirically tested the two sides of the arguments and as such remains a vacuum in the accounting and accounting related literatures. It is in the light of the above gap that this study seeks to study the comparative effect of using the above techniques on the performance of Brewery Industries in Nigeria with emphasis on the Champion Brewery Plc. The broad objective of this study is to compare the effect of C-V-P and A-B-C technique on the performance of Brewery Industries in Nigeria. However, the following specific objectives are:

1. To determine the extent to which the cost arrived at using CVP analysis increases profitability than ABC technique in Brewery Industries in Nigeria.
2. To ascertain the extent to which the cost arrived at using CVP analysis increases sales volume than ABC technique in Brewery Industries in Nigeria.
3. To find out the extent to which the cost arrived at using CVP analysis increases liquidity than ABC technique in Champion Brewery Plc.

Review of Related Literature

Over View of Cost Volume Profit Analysis and Activity Based Costing Technique

Cost volume profit (CVP) analysis and Activity Based Costing (A B C) techniques are among other manufacturing costing techniques employed by managers to help them understand the value of inputs and outputs in a production process. Management employs these techniques to be able to determine in a high degree of accuracy the cost per unit of production, pricing, ascertain production level and decision to make future investments.

Similarly, CVP analysis is a method of cost accounting used in managerial economics. It is based upon determining the break-even point of cost and volume of goods. It can be useful for managers making short-term economic decisions, and also for general educational purposes. It makes several assumptions in order to be relevant. It often assumes that the sales prices, fixed costs and variable cost per unit are constant. Running this involves using several equations, using price, cost and other variables equations and plotting them out on an economic graph.

It is also seen as a managerial accounting technique that is concerned with the effect of sales volume and product costs on operating profit of a business, it deals with how operating profit is affected by changes in variable costs, fixed costs, selling price per unit and sales mix of two or more different products.

Adeniji (2013) states that CVP analysis is one of the costing tools that managers use in order to understand the interrelationship between cost, volume and profit in an organization by focusing in interaction between the following elements: prices of products, volume of activity, variable cost per unit, total fixed cost and unit revenues are constant which is appropriate for small deviation from current production and sales, it assumes a sharp division between fixed and variable costs.

Activity Based Costing (ABC) technique on the other hand were developed to solve the problem of traditional costing. ABC measures process and activity performance, determines cost of business process outputs, process efficiency and effectiveness. ABC is a technique to quantitatively measure the cost and performance of activities, resources and cost object, including appropriate overhead costs, it captures organizational costs for factors of production and administrative expenses, and supplies them to the defined activity structure. ABC was designed to provide more accurate ways of assigning the costs of indirect and support resources to activities.

Ntiza and Boaz (2005) states that managers at all organizational levels perceive A B C data as more accurate and reliable than those generated by traditional costing and are willing to use them for decision making and performance evaluation.

According to Nweze (2009) CVP analysis is an application of marginal costing and seeks to study the relationship between costs, volume and profits at different activity levels and can be a useful guide for short-term planning and decision-making. The study further states that CVP analysis relation is a planning device that considers the inherent relationship between cost, volume of production and profit that is made. It asks such questions as: why, how, what and tries to give solution to them.

Adeniji (2013) explains Cost-Volume-Profit (CVP) analysis as an application of managerial costing that seeks to study the relationship between cost, volume and profit at different levels and can be relied upon for short term planning and decision-making. It further stated that CVP is referred to as break-even analysis that represents the position where total cost will equate the total revenue.

Robbin (2009) stated that in business organization, the activity-based costing methodology assign an organization's resources, costs through activities to the products and services provided to its customers. As such it has predominantly been used to support strategic decision such as pricing, outsourcing and identification and measurement of process improvement initiatives.

Appah and Binaebi (2013) described ABC technique as a costing technique that seeks both to allocate overhead to product costs on a more realistic basis other than production volume basis as well as showing the correlation between overhead costs and the activities that caused them. Kreuze and Newell (2001) in Abdullah and Tareq (2013) opined that ABC technique provide the means to identify cost bearing activities effectively and allocate costs to individual products. The study further stated that the basic aim of ABC is to cost activities not product on the basis of individual products' demand for those activities. The allocation basis (cost drivers) is the quantification of activities performed.

Ahmed (2011) defined ABC technique as a method of costing activities that are necessary for the production of product or services (ie activities being undertaken).

Nitin and Dalgobind (2013) inferred that Activity Based Costing (ABC) technique is a process where costs are assigned due to cause-and-effect relationship between costs and activities that drive these costs. It reveals the link between performing particular activities and the demands these activities make on the organization's resources, so it can give managers, facilities, regions or distribution channels both generate revenues and consume resources. The profitability picture that emerges from ABC analysis helps managers focus their attention and energy on improving activities.

Feridun and Al-Khadash (2006) investigated the link between practice of Activity Based Costing (ABC), Just-in-Tune (JIT), and Total Quality Management (TQM) as strategic initiatives and the improvement in corporation financial performance of 56 industrial shareholding companies in Jordan. Analysis shows that 26.8% of the companies under consideration use at least one of the strategic initiatives. The awareness level of importance of using the strategic initiatives is found to be significantly high among the financial managers, but such awareness is not reflected in the implementation of these initiatives. Furthermore, strong evidence emerges that the use of strategic initiatives leads to improvement in financial performance of the companies under consideration.

According to Kaplan and Anderson (2007), Time-Driven Activity Based Costing (TDABC) approach to overhead allocation. This is in integration with a lean environment in order to help provide accurate product unit costs. Actually, the TDABC requires fewer accounting transactions than the common ABC allocation method and still turns out an accurate computation of product unit costs, which suggests that it can coincide more with the Lean accounting approach to waste elimination.

Ibadin and Imosili (2007) opined that technological advancement in the area of manufacturing process which resulted in indirect cost increase has made a costing system based on volume related resources unnecessarily burdensome. This is because such costing system does not fit the present-day business realities as it distorts total production cost because the costing system treats indirect cost as homogeneous lumps to be allocated to product lines on a single volume related based.

Daniel (2012) defined cost volume profit (CVP) analysis as a managerial costing technique that helps to bridge the gap that widened latterly between accounting and budgetary control literature on one side and financial economic models evaluating flexibility in economic decision in particular real option literature on the other. The study further stated that cost volume profit analysis looks primarily at the effect of differing levels of activities on the financial results of a business the reason for the particular focus on sales volume is because, in the short-run, sales price and the cost of materials and labour are usually known with a degree of accuracy. Sales volume, however, is not usually so predictable and therefore, in the short-run profitability often hinges upon it.

CIMA (2013) official terminology describes activity-based costing as an approach to the costing and monitoring of activities, which involves tracing resources consumption and casting final outputs. Resources are assigned to activities and activities to cost objects. The later use cost drivers to attach activity costs to output. More so, ABC was first defined in the late 1980^s by Kaplan and Burns. It can be considered as the modern alternative to absorption costing, allowing managers to better understand product and customers net profitability. This provides the business with better information to make value-based and therefore more effective decisions. ABC focuses attention on cost drivers, the activities that cause costs to increase. Traditional, absorption costing tends to focus on volume related drivers, such as labour, hours, while activity-based costing also uses transaction-based drivers, such as number of orders received. In this way, long-term variable overhead traditional considered fixed costs, can be traced to products.

The study further stated that ABC techniques provides a more accurate method of product/service costing, leading to more accurate pricing decisions. It increases understanding of overheads and costs drivers; and makes costs and non-value adding activities more visible, allowing managers to reduce or eliminate them. ABC enables effective challenge of operating costs to find better ways of allocating and eliminating overheads. It also enables improved products and customer profitability analysis. It supports performance management techniques such as continuous improvement and score cards.

Patecharapom and Jitterat (2009) defined ABC techniques as a costing approach that assigns resource costs to cost objects such as products, services, or customers based on the activities performed. Activity Based Costing has gained recognition by being more accurate cost estimation and by providing traceable cost information when compared with Traditional Costing (TC) system such as CVP analysis. The study further stated that while ABC technique used multiple cost drivers that are related to unit-level, batch-level and product-level characteristics to allocate the overhead costs of the activities to the cost objects, traditional costing (TC) system

is a volume based overhead costing system. This approach relies on the assumption that each cost object use the same amount of overhead. This system tends to over cost for large-size or high-volume products and to under cost for small-size or low-volume products when product diversity exists within the same option.

Segovia and Khataie (2011) opined that the Ultimate reason for firms to adopt Activity. Based costing and management (ABC/M) is to improve their financial performance by managing their cost in such a manner that they control them and thus can reduce them. There is a significant difference between cost control and cost reduction. Companies can reduce their costs without necessarily controlling them. Cost control generally leads to intelligent cost reductions, e.g. lean companies. They stated that in today's global and competitive business environment cost control has become a decisive variable in the firm's financial success. The main objective is to shed some light as to whether how, when and where telecommunication companies can adopt ABC/M as a means for an effective cost management. It provides evidence as to whether or not ABC/M does have a positive effect on the firm's financial performance.

Monir (2009) started that traditional costing systems have worked well for many decades and may continue to be useful today to value inventory and measure the cost of goods sold. However, practitioners are facing various challenges using the traditional costing system CVP analysis in today's competitive environment. Cost and management Accountant in a globize world are now expected to be team players in such areas as product development, profitability analyses, quality process and improvement, and the evaluation of overall company performance. As a strategic cost management tool, activity-based costing (ABC) plays a vital role. The ABC model has revolutionized costing systems. It is method of analyzing business operations that leads to cost identification (e.g direct cost and indirect cost) and cost classifications based on activities.

CVP Analysis and Firm's Profitability, Sales Volume and Liquidity

Cost equations are combined with revenue equations to determine profitability at different levels of output. This is referred to as cost-volume profit (CVP) analysis. That is, net income equals total revenue minus total Cost; total cost, as noted above, equals average variable cost times the quantity of output plus fixed cost; and total revenue equals price times the quantity of output sold. Combing cost and revenue equations reveals that net income equals price times quantity of output sold minus average variable cost times the quantity of output minus fixed costs.

Where; P = price
 Q = quantity of output
 AVC = average variable cost
FC = fixed costs

Cost volume profit (CVP) analysis equally looks at the effect of sales volume on the financial result of a business. The reason for the focus on sales volume is because, in the short run, sales price, and the cost of materials and labour, are usually known with a degree of accuracy. Sales volume, however, is not usually predictable and therefore, in the short run, profitability often hinges upon it and which usually brings about firm's; liquidity.

CVP analysis allows a firm to determine a break-even point, the level of output at which total revenue equals total cost. The total cost and total revenue functions will be equal at some non-zero level of output is assured by the fact that at zero units of output, total costs will be positive as result of fixed costs and total revenue will be

zero. This is based on the assumption that the unit price for which a product can be sold is greater than the unit cost, so that total revenue increases faster than total cost as output increases. In addition, to estimate profitability across a range of output levels, firms use cost volume profit (CVP) analysis to determine whether projected sales are sufficiently beyond the break-even point to warrant production.

Activity Based Costing (ABC) Technique on Profitability, Sales Volume and Liquidity

Robin and Robert (2009) stated that companies have reduced their dependency on traditional accounting system by developing Activity Based costing management systems. Initially, managers viewed the ABC approach as a more accurate way of calculating product cost but activity-based costing has emerged as a tremendously useful guide to management action that can translate directly into higher profits which increase the liquidity of the organization. Moreover, Activity based costing approach is applicable across the spectrum of company functions and not just in the factory. Because ABC reveals the links between performing particular activities and the demands those activities make on the organization's resources, it can give managers a clear picture of how products, brands, customers, facilities, regions, or distribution channels both generate revenues and consume resources. The profitability picture that emerges from the activity-based costing analysis helps managers focuses their attention and energy in improving activities that will have the biggest impact on the organization.

Fully exploiting ABC as a guide to profitability, sales volume and liquidity, however, requires a conceptual break from traditional cost accounting system such as cost volume profit analysis and others and a willingness to act on the insights ABC analysis produces. Managers must refrain from allocating all expenses to individual units and instead separate the expenses and match them to the level of activity that consumes the resources in order to arrive at true cost of a product. Manager should separate the expenses incurred to produce individual units of particular product from expenses needed to produce different product or too sure different customers, independent of how many units are produced and sold.

Management must estimate the profitability of each product in order to make decisions about which products to produce and sell and how to price them. This in turn, requires an understanding of full cost per unit of each product. While the direct costs per unit may be determined easily, the indirect costs are less obvious and will have to be found through a costing methodology such as Activity Based costing technique. Direct costs will be treated in the same way under both traditional costing and Activity Based Costing technique. For direct costs, accountants measure a cost per product unit for each direct cost category. The two-costing method differs, however, in the way they assign the so-called indirect costs to products. Thus, the two costing approaches can give different picture of the profitability of individual products.

Empirical Review

Andi and Syamsuri (2020) studied the integration of cost volume profit analysis and activity-based costing technique in obtaining cost accuracy for decision making. Data for the study were collected through interview and analysed using descriptive quantitative method. The result of study showed that CVP is simpler and more straight forward approach, it may not be as accurate as ABC in allocating costs to specific products or services. On the other hand, ABC provides a more detailed and accurate view of costs but may be more complex and time consuming to implement.

Enkeleda and Etem (2022) studied the role of CVP Analysis as important indicator for planning and decision making in business environment. The study was done in manufacturing and servicing enterprise using econometrics model. Data were collected through structured questionnaire. The result showed that amount of product produced has positive effect on sales value to service companies and raising profit to the manufacturing business environment, also exist an important relationship between production and sales, CVP analysis contributes to growth profitability and break-even in the business environment.

Kavitta (2018) studied cost volume profit analysis with reference to Salem Steel Authority of India Ltd. The study was carried out to find out the problems of large-scale industries to maintain cost volume profit level and to determine their profit level from their operations. The study used ratio analysis and brake even point to analysis data collected. Result shows that management may use cost volume, profitability analysis to calculate the profit yield by a given amount of selling goods. CVP analysis is helpful to analyze the profitability position according to the cost and sales volume not only Salem Steel Plant but also useful for every organization to prevent future risks of the business.

Oluwagbamiga (2015) investigated to determine the adoption level of the new management accounting techniques and also to identify the factors influencing the choice of management accounting practices in the manufacturing organization with particular reference to Nigeria listed manufacturing organization. The study used descriptive and inferential statistics in the analysis of data collected, result shows that the new management accounting techniques such Activity Based Costing techniques (ABC) and Balanced Score Card have not been fully embraced by the manufacturing organizations in the developing economies. The practice of old management accounting technique such as CVP, marginal costing, accounting rate of returns are still on the increase in the present-day practice of management accounting. This is not because the new management accounting techniques are without prospect by the task of adequate awareness might not have been carried out.

Sadiq et al (2017) studied Cost Volume Profit analysis (CVP) as a management tool for decision making in small Business Enterprise within Bayero University. The study used non parametric studies and data was analyzed using pearson correlation coefficient, result show that there is no statistically significant difference between having the knowledge of a management accounting tools and its application. The study concluded that small business enterprise utilizes CVP analysis and it is recommended that CVP analysis and other management accounting tools be introduced to small business enterprises so that productivity can be improved.

Mohammed et al (2015) examined the impact/relationship between ABC adoption and implementation versus Tradition Costing technique in Iranian forging companies of Iran tractor manufacturing. Data were extracted from annual report of 240 quoted companies for the year 2014. The study used micro soft excel and SPSS software in the analysis of data. Results showed that there is no significant difference between cost every unit according to Traditional Costing and ABC system, also, there is no significant difference between gross profit of every unit according to Traditional costing and ABC system.

Chinedu et al (2018) studied the need to develop ABC technique in accounting practices among manufacturing firms in Nigeria as a tool for product costing. The study used parametric studies and the results showed there is extreme low adoption of ABC among manufacturing firms in Nigeria, possibly because of low knowledge of ICT. More so, ABC techniques improve efficiency, reduces operational cost and properly cost product better than traditional cost accounting system.

Azubuikwe et al (2017) studied Activity Based Costing and firm's value of manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The study used ex-post research design and multiple regression was employed to analyze data collected. The results showed that ABC technique effectiveness is significantly and positively related to firm's value. The results indicate that firms with greater degree of cost accountant competency, corporate resource facilitation, and price competitive force appear to have a higher effect on cost driver fitness, cost calculation accuracy, cost information creditability and cost reporting usefulness.

Azzouz Elhamma (2015) studied the relationship between activity-based costing, perceived environmental uncertainty and global performance. The empirical work adopted non parametric studies and result shows that the perceived environmental uncertainty influences significantly and positively the use of ABC. The study also found that the management accounting system based on ABC method results in a better performance for enterprises that have adopted it. The study also demonstrated that the firm operating in an uncertain and instable environment have an interest to adopt this new method of the management accounting but the firm operating in a certain environment are indifferent between adopting and not adopting this method. Finally, the result showed that the outcomes of the study are relevant to the literature on both ABC implementation and performance ABC, since they determine that the use of ABC results in improving in firm's performance.

Nilgun Kayati et al (2014) studied the effect of ABC systems on the performance of sale representatives: A field study in a Turkish firm. The result showed that ABC system is quite a useful method to make accurate and firm performance evaluation. When sales performance evaluating is dependent on simple measurements such as sales volume and gross project, the cost resulting from marketing activities are missed out and it leads to incorrect performance measurement of sales representatives.

Emergini, Steve E et al (2014) studied product cost management in developing Countries: Activity – Based costing with particular reference to manufacturing companies in developing country like Nigeria. Companies were sampled in the South east of the country using multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA). Results showed that there is no statically significant difference in cost reduction attained by ABC over Traditional costing. Profit realized in industrial and brewery sectors of the manufacturing companies surveyed were higher in ABC than traditional costing. The study recommended that ABC should be applied by manufacturing companies in Nigeria since any little difference in cost saving can influence management decision.

Terungwa (2012) Studied the practicability of implementing time-driven activity-based costing system in small service businesses in Benue State and analyzes profitability of it's varying customers. The study was carried out to establish if the application of ABC in small scale service-oriented businesses in Makurdi metropolis of Benue state will enhance their performance in terms of profitability. A random sample of small-scale business was studied using questionnaire and interview. The result showed that using ABC system in comparison with the existing method provides more data on cost and profitability of customers served.

Zhang and Che (2011) studied the effect of Activity Based Costing (ABC) techeque success implementation on the firm's performance among Chinese manufacturing companies. The previous empirical studies provide the evidence that the implementation of ABC could improve firm's both financial performance and non-financial performance. However, the researches on the relationship between ABC implementation and firm's performance are relatively few, especially in Chinese context. Due to the limitation of financial performance, this study investigates the role of ABC in predicting the improvements in firm's performance, namely

manufacturing and business performance among firms in China. Survey questionnaire was delivered to chief financial officers, financial control of 100 manufacturing firms listed on Chinese chamber of commerce and industry 2008 directory. The result showed that respondent generally achieved a moderate level of success of ABC implementation. The success of ABC implementation leads to the decrease in manufacturing cycle-time. In addition, ABC success implementation was found to be impact the attainment of target to costs, productivity, quality, profit, sales, liquidity as well as service.

Rafiu and Tajudeen (2012) examine the extent of adoption of Activity Based Costing (ABC) among manufacturing companies in Nigeria. A random sample of manufacturing companies was studied using questionnaire and the analysis of the study revealed that inability of the traditional costing systems to provide relevant cost was the most highly ranked reason in their decision to adopt ABC. The study further stated that Traditional methods of allocating overhead were therefore believed to be deficient in terms improving global competitiveness.

Oniyama (2011) studied the role of Activity Based costing on organization pricing system in foam and mattress industry. Using activity-based costing methodology in the analysis of data. The result shows that activity-based costing system allows an organization to have a realistic and effective costing procedure that can enhance organization manufacturing activities.

Al-Refa'ee (2012) identifies the extent of applying activity-based costing (ABC) technique in the field of iron and steel industry in Jordan. The study used non parametric statistics and result showed that most iron and steel companies of Jordan does not apply the activity-based costing system A B C, and the main reason for abstaining from applying the system is a firm conviction of the upper management, and the high costs of the application of the system.

Osahon (2014) Studied Financial Modeling in non-profit making organizations; the cost-volume profit approach. The study used questionnaire and the result revealed that CVP analysis as a technique of financial modeling is both a management tool for determining the impact of selling prices, costs and volume on profits and a conceptual tool. It helps management to focus on the objectives of obtaining the best possible combination of prices, volume, variable, cost and fixed costs. An advantage of the cost volume profit analysis model is its simplicity. Be that as it may, the price of such simplicity is a set of limiting assumptions that result in some loss of realism with one of the most troubling, being the use of single cost driver.

The study further stated that if CVP analysis is applied to a Multiple Production Company, it is assumed that there is a constant sales mix of products as the total quantity of units sold changes. In this connection, whenever assumptions are made, it is advisable to perform sensitivity analysis to determine whether and how the assumption effects decision. Also, ABC technique can be used to discard some of the simplifying assumption of the traditional CVP analysis by recognizing the existence of multiple or several cost drivers.

Nitin and Dalgobind (2013) studied current trends of application of Activity Based Costing (ABC) techniques. The study used non probability sampling in the analysis of data and the result showed that the model of activity-based costing can be used in every type of organization. It has been successfully implemented and used by many large companies like industries, institutions, or public sector. Moreso, Activity Based Costing (ABC) provides more accurate cost data as compared to traditional based costing system. It provides detailed information on the value-added and non-value-added activities performed by the organization. It also helps

managers to understand the true costs of providing products and services, and factor that drive these costs, while addressing other concerns such as customer satisfaction. It is a tool for managing complexity in manufacturing which provides activity-based information to help managers understand and eliminate complexity. It is also a communication tool between production and marketing and product design that help minimize product changes which create unnecessary complexity.

Methodology

The study made use of descriptive research design. Descriptive research design is a scientific method which involves the investigation of one or more variables which the researcher does not control or manipulate any of the variables, but only observes and measures them. This design is useful; considering the fact that the study is comparing the effect of C-V-P analysis and Activity Based Costing Techniques on organizational performance with emphasis on Champion Breweries Plc.

Sources of Data

Data used for the study is basically secondary source of data. This was generated from the selected company's financial statements. In order to collect data needed for the research, the following resources were utilized; Financial statement from 2013 to 2017 and notes along with the financial statement and the data in production units and internal audit departments.

Model Specification

Here, the study adopted ABC cost model as opined by Oniyama (2011) in Ibadin and Imoishi (2007) in the calculation of total cost of each product as shown below:

$$(TCP) P_n = D_c + \sum \{(ORA) (NA)\} (qnPN)$$

This was modified mathematically as follows:

$$Pfc = pfdc + \sum (oarou \times ssoa \times pfpocou) + \sum (oarlu \times pfpoclu)$$

$$Sac = sadc + \sum (oarou \times ssoa \times pfpocou) + \sum (oarlu \times ssoa \times spoclu) \dots\dots\dots 2$$

$$Lqc = Lqdc + (oarlu \times ssoa \times Lqpoclu) + \sum (oarlu \times ssoa \times Lqpoclu) \dots\dots\dots 3$$

Where; pfc: profitability cost,

Pfdc: profitability(s)' direct cost,

Oarou: overhead absorption rate for each organization unit.

Ssoa: suitable stimulus for overhead absorption

Pfpocou: profitability(s)' percentage regarding the overhead cost of each one of organizational units,

Oarlu: overhead absorption rate for each of line units,

Ssoa: suitable stimulus for overhead absorption

Pfpoclu: profitability(s)' percentage regarding the overhead cost of each one of line units,

Sac: sales' cost,

Sadc: sales' direct cost

Sapocou: sales' percentage regarding the overhead cost of each one of organizational units,

sapoclu: sales' percentage regarding the overhead cost of each one of line units,

lqc: liquidity(s)' cost,

lqdc: liquidity(s)' direct cost

lqpocou: liquidity(s)' percentage regarding the overhead cost of each one of organizational units,

lqpoclu: liquidity(s)' percentage regarding the overhead cost of each one of line units.

However,

Model Specifications are stated:

$n_1 \neq n_2$	1	
$CVP \neq ABC$		2
$CCVP \geq PAT > CABC$	3	
$CCVP \geq SAV > CABC$		4
$CCVP \geq LQTY > CABC$	5	

Where:

N_1 = Sample Size One

N_2 = Sample Size Two

CVP = Cost Volume Profit Analysis

ABC = Activity Based Costing Technique

CCVP = Cost Arrived at using CVP

PAT = Profit After Tax

CABC = Cost Arrived at using ABC

SAV = Sales Volume

LQTY = Liquidity

Analytic Techniques

The study analyzed and compared two means from the two techniques (CVP and ABC) using both descriptive and non-parametric statistics. The study made use of Mann-Whitney U test with aid of SPSS software in testing the hypotheses stated.

Thus, $U = n_1 n_2 \frac{\dots}{2}$

Where:

$U = \text{Mann-Whitney U Test} = \frac{n_1(n_1 + n_2) + n_2(n_1 + n_2) - n_1^2 - n_2^2}{2}$

N_1 = Sample Size One

N_2 = Sample Size Two

R_i = Rank of the Sample Size

Decision Rule: The critical value can be found in the table of critical values based on sample sizes ($n_1=n_2=17$) and a two-sided level of significance ($\alpha=0.05$). The critical value 87 and the decision rule is as follows: Reject H_0 if $U \leq 87$. At a degree of freedom of $N-2$ and at a chosen level of, significance, accept the null hypothesis if the calculated value is less than the t-table value otherwise reject.

RESULTS

Model designing and calculating the cost of each type of performance measure

a. The cost of arriving at profitability:

$Pfc = pfdc + \sum(oarou \times ssoa \times pfpocou) + \sum(oarlu \times ssoa \times pfpoclu)$

Where; pfs: profitability cost, pfdc: portability(s)' direct cost, oarou: overhead absorption rate for each organizational unit, ssoa: suitable stimulus for overhead absorption, pfpocou: profitability(s)' percentage

regarding the overhead cost of each one of organizational units, oarlu: overhead absorption rate of each of line units, ssoa: suitable stimulus for overhead absorption, pfpoclu: profitability(s)' percentage regarding the overhead cost of each one of line units.

b. The cost of arriving at sales:

$$Sac = sadc + \sum(oarou \times ssoa \times spocou) + \sum(oarlu \times ssoa \times spoclu)$$

Where; sac: sales cost, sadc: sales' direct cost, oarou: overhead absorption rate for each organizational unit, ssoa: suitable stimulus for overhead absorption, sapocou: sales' percentage regarding the overhead cost of each one of organizational units, oarlu: overhead absorption rate of each of line units, ssoa: suitable stimulus for overhead absorption, sapoclu: sales' percentage regarding the overhead cost of each one of line units.

c. The cost of liquidity:

$$Lqc = lqdc + \sum(oarou \times ssoa \times lqpocou) + \sum(oarlu \times ssoa \times lqpoclu) - pcbll$$

Where; Lqc: liquidity(s)' cost, lqdc: liquidity(s)' direct cost, oarou: overhead absorption rate for each organizational unit, ssoa: suitable stimulus for overhead absorption, lqpocou: liquidity(s)' percentage regarding the overhead cost of each one of organizational units, oarlu: overhead absorption rate of each of line units, ssoa: suitable stimulus for overhead absorption, lqpoclu: liquidity(s)' percentage regarding the overhead cost of each one of line units.

Table 3: The difference between Cost using CVP and ABC system in percentage

Variables	Cost percentage by using CVP system (%)	Cost percentage by using ABC system (%)
Profitability	48	60.5
Sales volume	34	27.5
Liquidity	18	12
	100	100

Source: Researchers' computation

Table 4: Kolmogroph-Smirnof's test to identify the normalness of variables distribution

Variables	No	Average	Std. dev.	Test	Meaningful level
Profitability	34	117672940.0000	118242943.41511	1.439	0.032
Sales volume	34	148555292.9412	186896740.76947	2.088	0.000
Liquidity	34	172967057.6471	218223569.31493	2.172	0.000

Source: Researchers' computation

In order to select appropriate statistics tests to analyze the collected data, the variables were assessed of normal distribution using knowledge Kolmogroph-Smirnof's test. From the results shown on Table --- 3, it was observed that the meaningfulness level of the test in the foregoing has been less than 0.05 for all of the variables. Thus, the study concluded that the distribution of all the variables has been abnormal and the non-parametric test was used for these variables.

Hypothesis Testing

H₀₁: Cost arrived at using CVP does not increase profitability than ABC technique.

From the test as shown on table 4 and Mann-Whitney U test's figures, we can observe that the mean cost rates calculated for profitability using ABC system is 115.85 and by using CVP it is 55.15 Arising from the criterion, U = 1,032.500 and meaningfulness level of p=0.000 and assurance level of 95%, the average rate of cost for profitability using both ABC and CVP system has shown meaningful difference (p>0.000). Thus, the result

suggests rejection of the null hypothesis and accepts the alternate which has it that cost arrived at using CVP increases profitability than ABC technique.

Table 5: Hypothesis Test Summary

Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig	Decision
The distribution of Independent samples PROFITABILITY is the same across categories of COST	Mann-Whitney U Test	.000	Reject the null hypothesis

Asymptotic significances are displayed. The significance level is .05.

¹ Exact significance is displayed for this test.

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

H₀₂: Cost arrived at using CVP does not increase sales volume than ABC technique.

The result of the test as shown on table 5 and the Mann-Whitney U test's figures below, it was observed that the mean cost rates calculated for sales volume by using ABC system is 81.76 and by using CVP system it is 89.24. Arising from the criterion, U = 3,930.500 and meaningfulness level of p = 0.540 and assurance level of 95%,

the average rate of cost for sales volume using both ABC and CVP system has not shown meaningful differences ($p > 0.05$). Thus, the result suggests upholding of the null hypothesis which states that cost arrived at using CVP does not increase sales volume than ABC technique.

Table 6

Hypothesis Test Summary

Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig	Decision
The distribution of SALES is the same across categories of COST	Independent samples Mann-Whitney U Test	.322	Retain the null hypothesis

Asymptotic significances are displayed. The significance level is .05.

¹Exact significance is displayed for this test.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

H03: Cost arrived at using CVP does not increase liquidity than ABC technique.

From the test as shown on table 6 and Mann-Whitney U test¹ figures, we can see that the mean cost rates calculated for liquidity using ABC technique is 111.37 and by using CVP analysis it is 59.63. Arising from the criterion, $U = 1,413.500$ and meaningfulness level of $p = 0.000$ and assurance level of 95%, the average rate of cost for liquidity using both ABC and CVP system has shown meaningful differences ($p > 0.05$). Thus, the result suggests rejection of the null hypothesis which has it that cost arrived at using CVP analysis does not increase liquidity than ABC technique and accept the alternate hypothesis.

Table 7

Hypothesis Test Summary

Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig	Decision
The distribution of LIQUIDITY is the same across categories of COST	Independent samples Mann-Whitney U Test	.000	Retain the null hypothesis

Asymptotic significances are displayed. The significance level is .05.

¹Exact significance is displayed for this test.

Figure 5.

Figure 6

Discussion

The discussions in this study are particularly on the result from the descriptive and non-parametric statistics which analyzed and compared two means from the two techniques (CVP and ABC). The study made use of Mann-Whitney U-test with the aid of SPSS software in testing the hypotheses stated, which were in accordance with the research questions and stated objective of the study. The results were also compared with the findings from prior studies by other researchers on related topics. The discussions were as shown below:

Cost Arrived at Using CVP Does not Increase Profitability than ABC Technique.

From the test as shown on table 4 and Mann-Whitney U test's figures, we can observe that the mean cost rates calculated for profitability by using ABC technique is 115.85% and by using CVP system, it is 55.15%. Arising from the criterion, $U=1,032.500$ and meaningfulness level of $p = 0.000$ and assurance level of 95%, the average rate of cost for profitability using both ABC and CVP has shown meaningful difference ($P>0.05$) thus, the result suggests rejection of the null hypothesis which has it that cost arrived at using CVP does not increase profitability than ABC technique. CVP combines its cost component into fixed and variable cost in the determination of cost for decision making, ignoring semi-variable cost, resulting in a higher profit looking at it without further investigation. While ABC technique determines cost using cost drivers (cost centres), thereby taking care of semi-variable cost which contributes to pushing down the declared profit.

This implies that the management of Champions Brewery Plc should endeavour to apply Activity Based Costing Technique (ABC in the determination of production cost and cost of other services. The essence of the application of ABC is to enable the organization get closer to true cost using cost drivers in order to arrive at true profitability. The problem of over or under costing of product will be eliminated with the application of ABC. The above findings are in agreement with the findings of other studies like Major & Hoper (2005), which states that Activity Based Costing Techniques, helps the organization in measuring the cost by studying and analyzing the activities to determine the activity that has added value, which will lead to maximizing the organization's profitability. More so, Monir (2009) states that traditional costing systems have worked well for many decades and may continue to be useful today to value inventory and measure the cost of goods sold. However, practitioners are facing various challenges using the traditional costing system-CVP analysis in today's competitive environment. Cost and management Accountant in a globalized world are now expected to be team players in such areas as product development, profitability analysis, quality process and improvement and the evaluation of overall Company Performance. As a Strategic Cost Management Tool, Activity Based Costing (ABC) plays a vital role in this regard.

Cost Arrived at Using CVP does not Increase Sales Volume than ABC Technique

The result of the test as shown on table 5 below and Mann-Whitney U test's figures, it was observed that the mean cost rates calculated for sales volume by using ABC system is 81.76 and by using CVP system it is 89.24.

Arising from the criterion, $U-3,930.500$ and meaningfulness level of $P= 0.322$ and assurance level of 95%, the average rate of cost for sales volume using both ABC and CVP system has not shown meaningful

differences ($P > 0.05$). thus, the result suggests upholding of the null hypothesis which states that cost arrived at using CVP does not increase sales volume than ABC technique. The implication of the result of this study is that Champion Brewery Plc should adopt the Activity Based Costing Technique (ABC) in order to attain its target cost which will help to fix the prices of its products, to be able to secure wider market with its attendant increase in sales volume. To give credence to the findings, Zhang and Che (2011) state that success of ABC implementation leads to the decrease in manufacturing cycle-time. In addition, ABC implementation was found to impact the attainment of target costs, Productivity, quality, profitability, sales volume, liquidity as well as service. Also, Marty (2004) states that management adopts ABC technique by the desire to improve costing accuracy get closer to the true cost and profitability which is the result of an increased sales volume of individual products and services.

Cost arrived at using CVP analysis does not increase liquidity than ABC technique.

From the result of the test as shown on the table 6 below and the Mann-Whitney U test's figures, it was observed that the mean cost rates calculated for liquidity by using ABC system is 111.37 and by using CVP system is 59.63. Arising from the criterion, $U = 1,413.500$ and meaningfulness level of $p = 0.000$ and assurance level of 95%, the average rate of cost for liquidity using both ABC & CVP system has shown meaningful differences ($p > 0.05$). Thus, the result suggests rejection of the null hypothesis which states that cost arrived at using CVP does not increase liquidity than ABC technique. The liquidity is very important to life of an organization. To achieve this, organizations should employ a sound costing technique such as Activity Based Costing Technique (ABC) in its costing system. As noted in the hypothesis test result in 5.1 above, champion Brewery Plc should adopt ABC which uses cost drivers in arriving at product cost, so that any profit made would be seen as true profit. Therefore, the liquidity of on organization can only be guaranteed, when there is true profitability. To corroborate these findings, the previous findings of other researchers such as Robin & Robert (2009), states that managers of Business firms viewed ABC approach as a more accurate way of calculating product cost. The study equally states that Activity Based Costing has emerged as a tremendously useful guide to management action that can translate directly into higher profits which increase the liquidity of the organization.

However, the above result was confirmed by the results of Independent Sample Waldwolfowitz runs test, Independent Samples Kolmogorov – Smirnov test, Independent Samples Kruskal – Walli's test and Independent Sample Jonckherrze – terpstra test for ordered alternatives with P-values of 0.000, 0.000, 0.000 and 0.000 respectively.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Activity Based costing technique is a new costing technique that provides a more accurate method of product/service costing, leading to more accurate pricing decisions which translate into increased profitability, sales volume and liquidity than when traditional costing system, CVP inclusive is used. ABC technique emerged due to new competition as a result of deregulation, which has also given companies greater freedom in getting prices and deterring the mix of product to offer, well managed service firms with a good understanding of their markets, consumers and information technologies that become much more profitable in a deregulated and more competitive environment (Hussian & Gumasekman) 2001 in (Ahmed, 2011). Companies seeking to thrive in a competitive business environment should as a matter of necessity reduce

their dependency on traditional accounting system by embracing Activity Based costing Technique. Managers viewed ABC approach a shore accurate way of calculating product. ABC has emerged as a tremendously useful guide to management action that can translate directly into higher profits which increases the liquidity of the organization. Moreover, activity-based costing is applicable across the spectrum of company functions and not just in the factory. It reveals the links between performing particular activities and the demands those activities make on the organization's resources. It can give managers a clear picture of how products, brands customers, facilities, regions, or distribution channels both generate revenues and consumer resources. The profitability picture that emerges from the activity-based costing analysis helps managers focuses their attention and energy in improving activities that will have the biggest impact on the organization (Rabin & Robert, 2009). To exploit ABC technique as a guide to profitability, sales volume and liquidity however requires a conceptual break from traditional costing technique such as cost volume profit analysis and others and a willingness to act on the insights ABC analysis produces. Managers must refrain from allocating ail expenses to individual units, instead separate the expenses and match them to the level of activity that consumes the resources in order to arrive at true cost of a product.

Recommendations

The researcher proffers the following recommendations in line with the findings of the study.

- a. Brewery industry in developing countries like Nigeria should develop management and core values that will promote the utilization of ABC in their costing system, so as to determine the true cost of product which will enhance profitability of the organization.
- b. Brewery industry in Nigeria should employ Activity Based Costing Technique to be able to determine in a high degree of accuracy the cost per unit of production, in order to get larger share of the market to increase sales volume.
- c. Brewery industry in developing countries like Nigeria should avail themselves of a software in the market which can facilitate the application of Activity Based Costing, which will help to guarantee the liquidity of the organization.

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